

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

A Tracer Study on the Bachelor of Agricultural Technology Graduates of Batch 2019 of Isabela State University – San Mateo Campus

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Abstract

A tracer review is one of the easiest ways to gauge the efficacy of a system. The study's aim was to determine the graduates' profile, the status of employability, the relevance of their course to their present job, the graduates' learning skills to their present job and to evaluate the quality of education at the ISU-San Mateo campus. Data were collected by sending online questionnaires with their active social media and email accounts to graduates and handing out questionnaires to graduates working nearby agencies and institutions. Findings from the study revealed that graduates revealed that their degree is relevant to their job, and they are equipped with different skills to compete in the global market but still experienced tight competition and no immediate vacancy that causes them to be on probation, part-time, and seasonally employed.

Keywords: Agricultural Technology; Employability; Graduate; Tracer Study

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1. Introduction

Education plays an important role in manpower development which can provide leadership to national development efforts. It forms the human capital required to promote at least two essential growth drivers-education and study. This research is important in order to understand how a university has done in terms of improving its students' competencies and preparing them for the work world (Cagasan, 2017).

Institutions engaged in human resource development through long-term and short-term programs have a responsibility to keep track of their graduates' success in evaluating accountability and whether their programs have impacted the person, organization, etc or not. Tracer research constitutes one type of analytical analysis that offers useful information for assessing the outcomes of a specific higher education institution's education and training. Such knowledge can be used in the sense of quality control to further improve the institution. (Mundo et. al., 2019) The graduates are seen as the strongest proof of the success of a program in terms of jobs and positions held. In addition, they provide a clear source of input about the

importance of the system in the current labor market.

The survey questions were related to the graduates' qualifications prior to their entry into higher education, their education background, their eligibilities, their employment, their length of time in looking job, the reasons for the delay of employment, the factors that facilitate their first or present job, employment status, the relevance of their college degree in their present job, their competencies learned in college that is useful in their job and assess the quality of education at ISU-San Mateo Campus. The Bachelor of Agricultural Technology is now in its fifth year of service and has been able to deliver the first batch of graduates in 2019, this paper looks at a tracer analysis to assess the importance of the curricula. The results obtained from the first batch of graduates will provide the necessary inputs to help the Campus develop its services. The Commission on Higher Education orders all Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to conduct a report on the tracer. Tracer studies are also expected of HEIs seeking accreditation from accrediting bodies such as the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and